

GOLD OPEN ACCESS AT CHARLES UNIVERSITY

Options of financing publication fees and discounts for CU authors

The gold route of open access stands for **publishing in an open access journal**. How to publish in the gold route is described in detail on the [website of the Open Science Support Centre of Charles University](https://library.cuni.cz/open-access) (library.cuni.cz/open-access).

Paid and so-called hybrid open access journals are associated with **article processing charges** (APC). These can be covered from the budget of a grant or research project (open access publishing costs for the duration of the grant are eligible, e.g. in projects within H2020, ERC, MEYS, etc.), or from the workplace budget (if funds for these fees are set aside).

More detailed information on open access to scientific information can be found on the website of the [Open Science Support Centre](https://library.cuni.cz/open-access) (library.cuni.cz/open-access). If necessary, contact your [open access faculty coordinator](#) or the [Open Science Support Centre](mailto:openaccess@cuni.cz) (openaccess@cuni.cz).

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Discounts on open access publishing fees for CU authors *

Vydavatelství	Forma slevy	Podmínky
American Chemical Society	250 USD off the base APC price	Corresponding author of Charles University when publishing in ACS journals; additional discount for members of the ACS Membership program.
Institute of Electrical and Electronics Engineers (IEEE)	5 vouchers for publication fees **	Corresponding author of Charles University; the author must register with the RightsLink Author (the author's handbook is available) and be correctly assigned to institution 37740: <i>Charles University (CU)</i> .
Karger Publishers	Full waiver of open access fees	Corresponding author of Charles University when publishing in both full open access and hybrid journals by Karger Publishers.
Lippincott Williams & Wilkins	Full waiver of open access fees for 5 articles	Corresponding authors from medical faculties of Charles University (1st, 2nd and 3rd Faculty of Medicine, faculties of Medicine in Hradec Králové and in Plzeň) in fully open and hybrid journals of Lippincott Williams & Wilkins / Wolters Kluwer Health.
MDPI	10% off the base APC price	Corresponding author of Charles University when publishing in MDPI journals .

* Discounts are regularly updated. You can find the latest version on the [website of the Open Science Support Centre](#).

** Vouchers are available to [all institutions involved in the consortium in the Czech Republic](#). Their distribution works on the principle of "first come, first serve"

